

Vietnamese Legal Framework on Information Security in Electronic Transactions in the Context of Digital Economy Transformation

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ABSTRACT: The three pillars of “The National Digital Transformation Program until 2025, with a vision towards 2030,” approved by the Prime Minister of Vietnam, are identified as E-Government, Digital Economy, and Digital Society. For Vietnam, advancing the digital economy and progressing towards a digital society presents an opportunity to narrow the gap with the world, creating new growth opportunities and serving as a core driver in national economic development. Electronic transactions are considered pivotal factors in realizing the digital economy. A robust legal framework related to security in electronic transactions is essential for the establishment of a strong electronic trading market (Vietnam’s E-Government Portal). Objectively assessing the legal provisions in Vietnam, it can be observed that regulations addressing information security issues in electronic transactions still contain provisions that are not fully aligned with contemporary trends. Through qualitative research methods, the authors of this study aim to identify shortcomings and deficiencies in the legal regulations governing information security in electronic transactions under Vietnamese law. Subsequently, they propose solutions to enhance this framework in the context of digital transformation.

Keywords: Electronic transactions, electronic transaction security, digital economy, Electronic Commerce Law

Introduction

The legal situation regarding information security in electronic transactions in the context of the digital economic transformation

Some proposals, recommendations for improvement

References

1. Introduction

The formation of contracts in e-commerce is becoming increasingly prevalent in Vietnam, as evidenced by the 2021 Vietnam E-commerce White Paper, constructed from official statistical surveys by the Ministry of Industry and Trade in 2020, involving over 8,000 businesses and 1,000 consumers. The analysis results reveal that more than 33% of Vietnamese businesses surveyed use electronic contracts in their business activities. In the context of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, the Prime Minister issued Decision No. 645/QĐ-TTg on May 15, 2020, approving the comprehensive plan for the national e-commerce development phase 2021-2025, with basic goals such as integrating online ordering functions into around 80% of e-commerce websites and having 50% of small and medium-sized enterprises engaged in business activities on e-commerce trading platforms.

Therefore, one of the requirements aimed at protecting the legitimate interests of parties involved in transactions is the need for a secure information mechanism in established electronic transactions. To operationalize this, the legal framework governing electronic transactions, particularly the formation of e-commerce contracts, must be stringent, specific, and feasible in practical application. However, certain limitations persist in this regard, necessitating prompt resolution to ensure the information security of parties entering into e-commerce contracts.

2. The legal situation regarding information security in electronic transactions in the context of the digital economic transformation

2.1. Information security in electronic transactions during the transaction initiation phase

In the field of Economics, the process of entering into contracts in general, as well as electronic transactions specifically, typically adheres to a specified sequence. The contract formation process involves the mutual expression of intent by the parties to reach agreements that give rise to rights and obligations. This process unfolds in two legally stipulated steps: the offer to enter into a contract and the acceptance of the contract offer. A contract is established when one party proposes an offer, and the other party accepts this proposal. The contracting process is carried out through electronic means and follows the general regulations regarding contract formation in civil law.

Based on Article 36, Clause 2 of the 2005 Electronic Transactions Law, it is stated: "In contract formation, unless otherwise agreed by the parties, the offer to enter into a contract and the acceptance of the contract offer may be made through data messages." Therefore, in the absence of any other agreement, the process of electronic contract formation consists of two fundamental steps: (1) Offering to enter into a contract; and (2) Acceptance of the contract offer. During the process of electronic contract formation, the information within the electronic contract obtained by one party from the counterparty may hold a certain value for the information provider. If this information is not kept confidential and used for the intended purpose, it can adversely affect the legitimate rights and interests of the information provider. Therefore, the law needs provisions aimed at ensuring the security and safety of information in electronic transactions.

In general, electronic transaction laws have institutionalized provisions regarding the rights and obligations related to information security during the contract formation phase. Based on Article 46, Clause 2 of the 2005 Electronic Transactions Law, stipulates: "Agencies, organizations, and individuals may not use, provide, or disclose information about personal privacy or information of other agencies, organizations, or individuals that they access or control in electronic transactions without their consent, except as otherwise provided by law." Similarly, Article 387, Clause 2 of the 2015 Civil Code of Vietnam states: "In the case where one party receives confidential information from the other during the contract formation process, they have a responsibility to safeguard the information and may not use that information for their own purposes or other unlawful purposes."

Therefore, when one party provides the other with necessary information related to electronic transactions, if the duty is violated, sanctions will be applied (Thao Anh 2023). Consequently, when the recipient also has the obligation to secure the information, violations will result in similar sanctions, ensuring the rights and obligations of the parties, especially third parties. Furthermore, during negotiations, parties may exchange crucial information they possess (such as business secrets, formulas, improvement strategies, product quality enhancements, product designs, new product development technologies, etc.), which are essential “assets” for businesses. Subsequently, if the contract is not concluded, the party that provided the information may face inherent risks if not adequately protected, such as the risk of the recipient or a third party using the information arbitrarily, causing disadvantages and harm to the information provider.

In the stage of proposing electronic contract formation, the transaction phase is susceptible to fraud and abuse as parties have yet to establish binding agreements. The obligation to secure information is addressed in the Principles of International Commercial Contracts (PICC) by Unidroit in 2016, under Article 2.1.16, which stipulates: “In the case of information provided in confidence by one party during negotiations, the other party is obligated not to disclose or use such information for purposes other than intended, whether or not a contract is subsequently concluded. When necessary, remedies for breaches of this obligation may include compensation based on the benefits gained by the disclosing party”. (Article 2.1.16 Principles of International Commercial Contracts 2016 Where information is given as confidential by one party in the course of negotiations, the other party is under a duty not to disclose that information or to use it improperly for its own purposes, whether or not a contract is subsequently concluded. Where appropriate, the remedy for breach of that duty may include compensation based on the benefit received by the other party).

Building upon the aforementioned principle, along with the obligation to provide information, the duty to secure information during the stage of proposing electronic commerce contracts should be designated as a distinct legal obligation to clearly define the rights and responsibilities of the involved parties. Consequently, this helps participants in electronic transactions to autonomously protect themselves, fostering awareness and a sense of responsibility for securing information in electronic transactions.

In addition to the provisions in the 2015 Civil Code and the 2005 Electronic Transactions Law of Vietnam, depending on the field of electronic transaction formation, Vietnamese law also contains regulations in specialized legal areas concerning the obligation of contracting parties to ensure information security in transactions in general and specifically in the context of forming electronic transactions. For instance, Article 14 of the 2010 Law on Credit Institutions outlines information security provisions for credit institutions; Article 25 of the 2012 Lawyers Law stipulates the rights and obligations of lawyers in securing client information from the stage of contract signing for legal consulting services; Clause 2 of Article 21 of the 2019 Labor Code specifies commitments of parties in labor contracts related to business secrets, confidential implementation of technology by employers, and sanctions in case of a breach of information security obligations under the contract.

Therefore, by stipulating that parties must implement security measures and refrain from engaging in activities that may disclose electronic transaction data during the contract formation stage, Vietnamese law has initially ensured the establishment of transactions in a secure manner. However, the effectiveness of these security measures is contingent upon compliance with the provisions of the Law on Information Technology 2006, the Telecommunications Law 2009, the Network Information Security Law 2015, etc. Additionally, during this stage, parties will use digital signatures as an electronic verification method to ensure that the information sender and receiver are accurately identified as the intended participating entities, preventing information leakage that could allow third parties to intervene (Nguyen Thi Long & Huynh Minh Quang 2022, 33).

2.2 Securing information in the execution phase of electronic transactions.

Executing electronic transactions in general and implementing electronic contracts, in particular, is the process by which the involved parties “actualize” the rights and obligations previously agreed upon in the contract, ensuring compliance with legal provisions, including those related to electronic transaction security. According to Article 35 of the 2005 Electronic Transactions Law: “The parties have the right to agree to use electronic means in the formation and execution of contracts; the formation and execution of electronic contracts must comply with the provisions of this Law and contract law; when forming and executing electronic contracts, the parties have the right to agree on technical requirements, authentication, conditions ensuring integrity, and security related to that electronic contract.” Additionally, security issues related to the implementation of electronic contracts in the commercial field are specified in Clause 4 of Article 289 of the 2005 Commercial Law: “Entities are obliged to keep confidential the business secrets granted in commercial contracts.”

However, during the execution of electronic contracts, Vietnamese law on electronic transactions only includes certain provisions regarding the rights and obligations related to information security in the contract implementation phase, and these are specified in various fields. Specifically:

Firstly, regarding the security of information for participants in electronic transactions. During the execution of electronic transactions, ensuring the security of information for the participating entities is one of the requirements to guarantee security in electronic transactions. This ensures the safety of the involved parties and prevents other entities with malicious intentions from harming or disrupting the collaboration of the participating entities in electronic transactions. In the realm of protecting consumer rights, Article 6 of the Consumer Protection Law of 2010 stipulates: “1. Consumers are ensured the safety and confidentiality of their information when engaging in transactions, using goods, and services, except when authorized state agencies require disclosure,” or Article 19 of the Law on Network Information Security of 2015 states: “Organizations and individuals processing personal information must implement appropriate management and technical measures to protect the personal information they collect and store; comply with standards and technical regulations on ensuring network information security.”

In the current context, personal data is information in the form of signs, writing, numbers, images, sounds, or similar forms in the electronic environment that is associated

with a specific person or helps identify a specific person. Personal data includes basic personal data and sensitive personal data based on Article 2, Clause 1 of Decree No. 13/2023/ND-CP on the protection of personal data in Vietnam. Thus, personal data is not only information generated from individual activities but when combined with other stored data, it can identify a specific person. Therefore, the data of one party in the process of conducting electronic commerce transactions must be identified, and the obligation of the other party to secure the provided data arises only for transaction execution purposes. However, not in every electronic transaction can either party agree on the “obligation to secure information,” so it is necessary to stipulate this obligation even when the parties do not agree, except in cases where the parties agree otherwise.

Secondly, regarding the parties and other terms of electronic transactions. In addition to regulations on securing information for parties participating in transactions, the law has not yet addressed issues related to securing fees in electronic transactions, as well as the time and place for fulfilling obligations in electronic transactions. Particularly, in the electronic transaction environment where participating entities often do not know each other, regulations on the security of time and place for fulfilling contractual obligations will help participants avoid the attention of fraudulent entities seeking to misappropriate data or assets. Currently, the 2005 Electronic Transactions Law does not provide specific regulations on this matter, so there are no applicable sanctions for handling damages when they occur.

Furthermore, the choice of payment methods is also a crucial aspect in entering into electronic contracts because the involved parties may not meet in person for payment. Therefore, specific and detailed regulations are necessary. In Vietnam, there are intermediary companies facilitating online payments, serving as connectors between banks, buyers, sellers, and participants in electronic transactions. However, payment raises legal issues that need resolution, such as security, ensuring safety, and facilitating transactions. The Electronic Transactions Law mentions “intermediaries” in electronic transactions but does not provide specific regulations on the rights and obligations of these entities in electronic transactions, especially regarding information security obligations. This lack of specificity poses challenges in ensuring consistency in the management of secure, reliable transactions and customer protection. Additionally, Article 14, Clause 3 of the 2010 Law on Credit Institutions stipulates the need to “ensure that transaction information of customers is not disclosed.” However, the law does not establish specific measures or standards regarding the level of security and information safety when intermediaries handle payments in electronic transactions.

2.3 Securing information in electronic transactions at the termination stage of the electronic transaction.

At the point of terminating an electronic transaction, it is observed that the rights and obligations of the parties have been executed based on the initial agreed-upon purposes. However, the obligation to secure the entire information and data of one party for the other does not terminate simultaneously with the effectiveness of the contract (Dao Thi Minh Ngoc et al., 2022). In other words, if data provided by one party for the purpose of contract performance is used for different purposes by the other party after the termination of the

contract, causing damage, proportional compensation is required. Nevertheless, according to regulations, compensation is referred to in provisions related to “compensation for damages outside the contract,” but there is no mechanism for the parties to compensate by agreement when the contract has been terminated. In other words, it is necessary to establish regulations on compensation for damages caused by the violation of information security obligations regardless of the validity of the contract (Hoang Thi Kim Chi, 2016).

Although Vietnamese law does not have direct provisions on securing the information of the subjects, transaction parties, and payment methods, there are relatively specific regulations regarding storage requirements to establish evidence, and legal documents, as well as to ensure authenticity and security during the termination phase of electronic transactions, aiming to ensure that transactions are conducted safely even after the termination of electronic transactions. Specifically, Article 289(4) of the 2005 Commercial Law stipulates the obligations of traders receiving rights: “... 4. Keep confidential the trade secrets that have been licensed, even after the termination or expiration of the commercial licensing agreement,” indicating that the law has anticipated and regulated security as an obligation in specific sectors such as commerce with confidential content about trade secrets - a crucial element for a business from initiation to termination with any other party in the business environment (Nguyen Thi Long & Hoang Minh Quang, 2022, p. 34).

In terms of content, Article 15 of the 2005 Law on Electronic Transactions stipulates that in cases where the law requires documents, records, or information to be stored, these can be stored in the form of data messages if they meet the following conditions: (i) The content of the data message can be accessed and used for reference when necessary; (ii) The content of the data message is stored in the format in which it was initiated, sent, received, or in a format that accurately represents the content of that data; (iii) The data message is stored in a certain manner that allows the identification of the origin, destination, date, and time of sending or receiving the data message; (iv) The content and storage period for the data message are carried out in accordance with the legal regulations on storage. Article 10 of the 2011 Storage Law specifies: “Ensure the safety and security of electronic storage documents: (i) Organizations have the responsibility to periodically inspect and ensure the safety of the electronic document management system; (ii) Organizations implement measures to ensure security and safety in accordance with legal regulations in managing electronic storage documents.”

However, these regulations are not consolidated into a specific law but are scattered across various fields such as notarial services, finance, and banking (Article 17 of the Information Technology Law 2006; Article 64 of the Notarization Law 2014; Circular No. 134/2017/TT-BTC guiding electronic transactions on the securities market; Circular No. 19/2021/TT-BTC guiding electronic transactions in the field of taxation...), commerce, treasury, bidding, and enterprises.

Therefore, the Vietnamese legal system has formulated several legislative documents on the security and storage of information related to electronic transactions across various sectors (Trương Nhật Quang 2020, p.38). The majority of these documents contain provisions on the security of electronic transactions after their conclusion, aiming to

ensure legal validity and convenience for the widespread utilization of electronic transactions in daily life, meeting the requirements of electronic transactions. However, these provisions are often general and scattered across various documents, leading to challenges in accessibility and lacking effectiveness in the enforcement of legal regulations on the security of electronic transactions.

3. Some proposals, recommendations for improvement

The security of information related to the establishment, implementation, and termination of electronic transactions by the parties must be regulated rigorously, and consistently, and ensure the interests of all parties involved in the transaction. In the transition to the digital economy, although our legal system has regulations on the information security of the parties in electronic transactions, these regulations are not yet fully feasible and effective. Therefore, to encourage entities to confidently participate in electronic commerce in general and electronic transactions in particular, it is necessary, first and foremost, to refine and establish a legal framework that is strict, specific, and emphasizes high information security. Based on the legal realities presented, the authors propose some specific solutions to improve regulations on information security in electronic transactions in the context of transitioning to a digital economy, as follows:

Firstly, in the stage of entering into electronic transactions, it is necessary to supplement Article 4 of the Law on Electronic Transactions of 2005 with definitions for “electronic signature,” “digital signature,” “biometric signature,” “image signature,” and “secure electronic signature.” This amendment aims to comprehensively regulate and cover various forms of electronic signatures, providing a basis for the competent authorities to assess the legality of these forms. Additionally, Chapter III of the Law on Electronic Transactions of 2005 should be supplemented with provisions on electronic identification and electronic verification. This ensures that entities participating in electronic transactions have a basis for applying appropriate security measures. Verification is the process of establishing or confirming the credibility of an entity, meaning the information provided by a person or about something is accurate. Verification is a particularly important step to ensure the security of information system operations. Authenticating an object also means recognizing the origin of the object, while authenticating a person often involves verifying their personal identification.

Second, during the execution of electronic transactions, it is necessary to supplement Article 46 of Chapter 6 of the Law on Electronic Transactions of 2005 regarding the conditions for ensuring the safety of electronic transactions. The legal documents related to security conditions are stipulated in various stages, especially during the execution phase, to facilitate easy access for entities to electronically conclude contracts with specific requirements. This aims to fulfill the obligations within the contracted agreements. Specifically: (1) The “Recording” Requirement: A third party is not allowed to copy the document and send it multiple times to the recipient without the sender’s knowledge. (2) The “Signature” Requirement: The recipient must identify the sender and verify whether the sender has genuinely sent the information. (3) The “Integrity”

Requirement: The recipient should be able to determine whether the information has been altered during the transmission process.

At the same time, supplement provisions in Article 37 of the 2005 Law on Electronic Transactions regarding the responsibilities and rights of the parties when accessing and performing the duty of securing electronic transactions. Add regulations on the rights and obligations of the “intermediary” in electronic transactions, especially provisions on the duty to secure information of the “intermediary” in electronic transactions in general and in the role of a payment intermediary.

Third, during the termination phase of electronic transactions:

Firstly, supplement provisions in Article 13 of the 2011 Archives Law regarding the conversion of paper documents to electronic documents, conversion methods, conditions for compliance, and the value of electronic documents after conversion.

Secondly, expand the scope of regulation as stipulated in Article 1 of the 2011 Archives Law in storage activities in the private sector, thereby establishing a basis of evidence when disputes arise. In terms of regulatory scope, the law regulates the rights and obligations of organizations, agencies, and individuals in storage activities in both the private and public sectors. Regarding the applicable subjects, the law applies to political organizations, state agencies, the Vietnam Fatherland Front, political-social organizations, socio-professional political organizations, social organizations, socio-professional organizations, economic organizations, enterprises, armed forces, and related organizations and individuals.

Thirdly, add provisions on the responsibilities of relevant entities during the termination phase to Article 35 of the 2005 Law on Electronic Transactions: “Participants must be responsible for the data message and must not disclose information or secure transactions during specific phases.”

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